

CHARACTERIZATION OF HOST-PATHOGEN INTERACTIONS IN XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA INFECTIONS TO DEVELOP SUSTAINABLE BIOCONTROL STRATEGIES

D'ATTOMA G.**

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Xylella fastidiosa (Xf) is a plant pathogenic xylem-limited bacterium, recently introduced in Europe, whose outbreak, in the Southern area of the Apulia region, is causing a severe disease, the 'olive quick decline syndrome' (OQDS), on olive trees. My PhD research project is focused on the characterization of the biological mechanisms involved in the host-pathogen interactions occurring during Xf infections. Initial efforts have been addressed to characterize the bacterial genotype recovered from the infected hosts in Apulian foci. Genetic characterization, based on Multi Locus Sequence Typing (MLST), has revealed that Xf CoDiRO strain, so far univocally detected in Apulia, belongs to the sequence type "ST53" within subspecies *pauca*. Since diseases induced by Xf have no chemical cure and its pathogenic mechanisms are not completely understood, the following approaches are proposed to develop strategies of biocontrol. State-of-the-art knowledge demonstrates that the virulence of the pathogen relies on a fine balance between more motile bacterial forms, able to move and proliferate within xylem vessels, and sticky cells forming a biofilm, which are responsible for vessels blockage and insect acquisition. This different behavior is regulated by a cell density-dependent diffusible signaling factor (DSF), produced by *rpfF*-gene, that initiates a transduction cascade resulting in up- or down-regulation of several genes. DSFs produced by CoDiRO strain were analyzed by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry analysis. Preliminary results showed that a family of unsaturated fatty acids with a chain length of 12-18 carbon atoms is produced. Their further full characterization is in progress by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). The characterization of these molecules will have a direct application in a "pathogen confusion" strategy for reducing the impact of Xf-infections, by altering DSF level in planta and lowering its virulence. A plant viral-based vector, harboring the *rpfF*-gene, has been engineered to induce its transient expression. Experiments will verify if, upon DSF accumulation, Xf will be less motile and more adhesive to the surface of xylem vessels, thus showing a decreased virulence in infected plants. Limited knowledge is available on the relationship between microbial communities and their effects on the expression of symptoms in Xf-infected plants. Experiments are planned to characterize the microbiome in the xylem of tolerant and susceptible olive cultivars either by sequencing or bacteria isolation. These studies aim at developing a control strategy based on the alteration of microbial communities resident in olive and the possible identification of endosymbiont(s), able to colonize Xf-infected tissues, reducing the severity of symptoms.

SYSTEMIN INVOLVEMENT IN THE PRIMING OF TOMATO ENDOGENOUS DEFENCES

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To defend themselves against different biotic and abiotic stressors, plants use direct and indirect defence strategies. The former directly affects the susceptibility and/or the